

Microdetermination of Chromium : Dichromate Ion

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A simple photometric method for the microdetermination of dichromate has been developed. Use has been made of the reaction that ferrous cyanide on oxidation gives the ferrous-ferric cyanide complex which is a blue precipitate. At low concentrations, and under some specific conditions, however, precipitation does not occur and the extent of colour development can be directly related to the amount of oxidation. Interference of several diverse ions has been also studied. The method is highly sensitive and precise (RSD 1.8%). Beer's law was followed within the range of approximately 4-50 ppm in a final volume of 50 ml.

IN the course of studies carried out in our laboratories, a kinetic study on some oxidation-reduction reactions appeared to be exclusively dependent on the availability of a micro method for the quantitative determination of the oxidation product(s) of some reactions. Since one of the most suitable techniques in micro scale analysis is the spectroscopic finish, our attention was drawn to the utilisation of such a procedure and, in particular, the intense blue colouration of the hexacyanoferrates of iron. The extremely low solubility product of prussian blue, $\log K_{sp} = -40.52$,^{1,2} had probably hindered the attempts of devising a quantitative colorimetric procedure based on the formation of such an intensely coloured compound. The authors of this paper were able to avoid this difficulty and the estimation of chromium (as dichromate or chromate), was done satisfactorily and with high sensitivity and accuracy. In certain respects, it is far more sensitive and gives better results than the common reagents for chromium such as, chromotropic salt, reported in literature³⁻⁵.

Experimental

Optimization of Conditions

Based on the observations collected from the preliminary experiments, the following system was initially developed: 1 mole of hexacyanoferrate(II) was mixed with 0.5 mole of potassium dichromate and 1 mole of ferrous ammonium sulphate, in acidic medium (H_2SO_4); the optical density was recorded directly after dilution to the mark against a reagent blank at 715 nm using a 2 cm cuvette. Under these conditions, the molar absorptivity was $\epsilon_{715\text{ nm}} = 71,200$. A straight line calibration curve, which passes slightly above the origin, was obtained. However, after standing for 10-15 min two observations were made: (a) the blank developed a faint

colour; (b) the readings showed a measurable decrease. In addition, a precipitate could be observed on standing for a few hours. To overcome this drawback, the following were examined: complexing agents (NTA, DCTA, EDTA, tartrate, citrate, and phosphate); preventive colloids (cetavlon and gelatin); other diluents (distilled water, 2 to 4*N* H_2SO_4 , aqueous ethanol, and aqueous acetone). Of these, EDTA and gelatin were found to increase the molar absorptivity to $\epsilon_{715\text{ nm}} = 112,000$, a value higher than that for most sensitive spectrophotometric methods⁵. It was found that 5 ml aliquot of gelatin had to be added before all other reagents while 3.5 ml of EDTA are to be added before dilution to the mark with *N* H_2SO_4 , which proved to be the most suitable diluent. Under these experimental conditions, the colour was stable for 30 min after 15 min developing time.

Interference

The effect of some common cations and anions on the sensitivity of the suggested method for dichromate were tested and the results are given in Table 1.

Elimination of Interference Effect of Some Cations

The possible interfering effect caused by some cations can simply be eliminated using cationate resin exchanger (H-form). By this means, the cation(s) containing $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ sample solution has to be percolated through the resin; thus, the cation(s) is trapped by exchanging the H-ions of the resin; $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ anion has no tendency for the resin and, therefore, passes out for the determination by the recommended procedure.

Precision

The precision of the method was tested by replicate analyses (11 aliquots) of 1 ml of a $10^{-3}N$ dichromate solution by the recommended procedure. This yielded a standard deviation of 1.8%.

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TABLE I—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON DETERMINATION OF DICHROMATE ION

Ion	Added as	Upper limit permissible without interference (ppm)
Cl ⁻¹	Sodium chloride	1700
NO ₃ ⁻¹	Sodium nitrate	350
CO ₃ ²⁻	Sodium carbonate	300
Pb ²⁺	Lead nitrate	200
Zn ²⁺	Zinc chloride	50
Ni ²⁺	Nickel chloride	20
Mn ²⁺	Manganous chloride	50
Sn ²⁺	Stannous chloride	10
Co ²⁺	Cobaltous sulphate	5
Cu ⁺¹	Cuprous chloride	50
Cu ²⁺	Copper sulphate	40
Tartrate	Potassium tartrate	10
Citrate	Ammonium citrate	5
Oxalate	Sodium oxalate	50
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	Sodium persulphate	5
(C ₆ H ₅ .CO.O) ₂	Dibenzoyl peroxide	5

Reagents

N.B. All preliminary experiments were carried out on potassium dichromate. The following solutions were prepared :

Standard potassium dichromate, 10⁻³*N*.

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(II), 2 × 10⁻³ in air-free water. The solution was prepared fresh every day.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate in *N* H₂SO₄, 2 × 10⁻³*M*. EDTA, 10⁻¹*M* from AR grade disodium salt.

Gelatin, 0.1%. The solution was prepared fresh every day.

Calibration curve and procedure

Transfer into 50 ml standard flasks the following solutions in the given order and shake after each addition : 5 ml of 0.1% gelatin, 2.5 ml of 2 × 10⁻³*N* potassium hexacyanoferrate(II), 0.1–1.4 ml aliquots of 10⁻³*N* potassium dichromate test solution, 2.5 ml of 2 × 10⁻³*N* ferrous ammonium sulphate in *N* H₂SO₄, and 3.5 ml of 0.1*M* EDTA (disodium salt). Immediately dilute the constants of the flasks to 50 ml with *N* H₂SO₄ and measure the absorbance of each

solution 15–45 minutes from the time of preparation in 1 cm cuvettes at 715 nm against a reagent containing no dichromate by the Unicam SP600 spectrophotometer. Under these conditions a straight line calibration curve, which passes slightly above the origin, was obtained. Beer's law followed in the concentration range 0.4–50 μg Cr₂O₇²⁻/50, ml, and then a negative deviation was observed. 0.1 ml of 10⁻³*N* K₂Cr₂O₇ = 4 μg Cr₂O₇²⁻.

Unknown Sample

Use this procedure in the same way for unknown solutions containing 0.4–50 ppm of Cr₂O₇²⁻, using sample volumes containing about 4–50 μg of dichromate.

Results and Discussion

The proposed method for dichromate can be applied down to 0.4 ppm if 10 ml of sample are available and up to 50 ppm in a 1.4 ml test sample. It can be seen from these experimental results that though the selectivity of this method is not so high, the precision and the sensitivity on the other hand are quite good. It is interesting to note that the presence of EDTA caused no problem because of its strong complexation tendency, as it appears here to have no effect on the basic nature of the system. This can be seen to be true since no change was found in the spectra. The maximum absorption still occurs at 715 nm with enhanced intensity.

It is worthy to point out here that precipitation of the blue coloured species does not occur, yet the species log *K_{sp}* is very low. It is probable that the addition of gelatin serves to stabilise the material as a colloidal suspension as with many other methods

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